

The Role Of Formal Education In Farm Productivity And Farmer's Socio-Economic Development In District SWAT

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 01, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: September 01, 2021</p> <p>Keywords : Formal Education, Farm Productivity, Socio-Economic Development</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5368413</p>	<p><i>Education's role in agricultural productivity is commonly underestimated as compared to other sectors of the economy, yet the economic implications of formalized schooling on the farm have long been studied. In this research it is suggested that educational attainment has, indeed, long been a contributing factor in farming output, earnings, and labor mobility. More specifically, knowledge and skill have been instrumental dynamics of the differentiation amongst output, income, and transferability. The main objective of the study was to find out the impact of education on farm productivity and farmers socio-economic development. The study was conducted in two villages of district Swat, i.e. Kanju and Dherai. A total of ninety farmers were selected from both villages which become 10% of total in the area. The study concluded that maximum number of farmers received trainings on different topics related to farming. Majority have applied new techniques on their farms/cultivable land which resulted in better production and increased income. These trainings have also made their work easy. Most of the members received quality agricultural inputs. They found these better as compared to the market inputs. The plots demonstration on farm land has enabled the farmers to learn a lot of farming techniques.</i></p>

Introduction

Development strategies in the contemporary developing world increasingly emphasize the cruciality of education as catalyst of the development process through its positive impact on productive efficiency as well as equity in distribution. It is, therefore, important to examine the role of education in new emphasis. Enhancement in the educational level of a nation opens new avenues of sounder thoughts and views. Education is responsible for a transparent change in attitudes. It always says welcome and fare well forever to beneficial as well as detrimental attitudes and thoughts respectively. Thus education provides basis for evolution of human nature towards the fellow beings in the society. In the modern age, the progress of the country as well as prosperity of the masses is entirely dependent on the literacy rate of the people. Nodoubt that education is the sole panacea of all the ills of Pakistani society (Daraz, 2021). It is bound to bring a prominent change in the thoughts and attitudes of human beings. But to grow more food is the cry of the hour to satisfy the needs of the population of our country which is growing like a bomb. So the emphasis must be given on the fact that grower communities should be well informed and educated to quit the orthodox methods of farming and say welcome with broad and open mind to the modern technology, the vital requirement of enhancing the productivity as well as prosperity of the country to shed the shell of poverty forever, the root ill of all the other ills of the society. It is one of the requisites for socio-economic change. Education must be given the same priority, as defense of a country because developed and properly implemented education system is the cornerstone of a country's development. In case our national priorities are not changed soon. The economic, social and political fabric of Pakistan may degenerate to an unsustainable level (Ahamed, 1999)

Goldin and Katz are prolific authors of historical examination of and theoretical contributions to the value of education in regards to economic growth, labor productivity, income disparity, and technological advancement. In their publication "The Race between Education and Technology (Cambridge, MA: Belknap Press of Harvard University Press, 2008), they describe education as a converse force of technology, putting the two in a "race" that determines the socioeconomic returns to education and the wage premium that may result. Moreover, modern economic growth, characterized by technological innovation and human capital, has made the twentieth century the "American Century". Goldin and Katz stress the importance of education's supply growth through the first three-quarters of the twentieth century, and label this ascent as the most critical push toward income equality, higher productivity, and labor-skill alignment. Equally, the last-quarter of the twentieth century has been marred with heightened income disparity, productivity sluggishness, yet continued technological advancement. The common thread between these recent trends is a evident slowdown in the growth of educational supply (Ullah & Malik, 2020). The role of education can't be denied in any field for improvement

and better results. Education enables us to understand and implement projects in order to live lighter on the planet, whilst also caring for the planet, and our selves through the ways in which we use and distribute resources. Without education the development of a Permanent Culture would be impossible. Education is needed to transmit the newly evolved ideas and practices that emanate from different streams of thought and disciplines (Khan, 2020).

The literacy rate in rural areas is low and needs to be enhanced. As in rural areas majority of people depend on natural resources and agriculture, so for development and awareness in all aspects more schools and institutes should be established. Education is the back bone for any change and if the farmers are literate the agriculture sector will be developed and productivity will increase. The selection of this topic was based on how much formal education affect the productivity of crops. Agriculture sector can be more developed if the farmers are educated they will learn new techniques and will be able to easily adopt them. Most of the farmers are uneducated so the productivity is less, if the upcoming generation is highly qualified they will modernize the agriculture and there will be a rapid increase in the productivity. The selected title formal education plays a vital role to create awareness the farmers to adopt new techniques and technologies to improve their productivity. This study was conducted with the following objective; “To investigate the impact of formal education on farm productivity of major crops and socio-economic development of farmers in the study area”.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The inconsistent empirical results of education's impact on agricultural output are mostly attributable to four issues: (i) how to quantify the variable "education," (ii) whose education needs to be taken into account, and (iii) where it should be taken into account. what it means, and (iv) to whom it means it? The first two concerns the construction of the variable "education" in empirical studies. The value of formal education in various farm situations is addressed in the last two issues also to various farmers working in the same area. The first two concerns are addressed by Lockheed et al. (1980) and Phillips' length and width (1994). When it comes to the question of “whose education matters” in agricultural development, various studies have looked at the education of various people, such as the education of the head of the farming household, the average education of the household, the maximum education of any household member, and the minimum level of education of any household member over the age of 14 (Alene & Manyong 2007; Asadullah & Rahman 2009). Schultz (1975) claimed that in a mechanised farm environment, education is more important than in a traditional one. The ability of farmers to deal with the disequilibrium created by modern technology adoption is largely a result of their education. As a result, more educated farmers adjust better and faster than those who are less educated or illiterate (Hojo, 2004). According to a study conducted in Ethiopia, adding one year of formal schooling to the average villager's educational attainment had a considerably greater influence on farm output than raising household educational attainment by one year (Weir, 1999). Furthermore, due to common mutual learning among farmers in Uganda, social returns to schooling outperformed individual returns. This showed that an educated neighbour may influence an illiterate farmer by exchanging knowledge and ideas, implying that positive externalities from schooling lead to increased agricultural productivity, stressing the importance of government action in the agricultural sector (Appleton and Balihuta, 1996).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This section deals with sampling techniques and data collection procedures and analyzed. It also explained the sampling techniques and field work. The purpose of the study was to find out the role of formal education in farm productivity. The study was conducted in district Swat.

Universe of the Study: The dependence of 70% people of the Swat is on agriculture. The two villages of district Swat i.e. Kanju and Dherai were selected because it was easier for the researcher to conduct the research and collect the data from the respondents. According to the local government union council office the population of these two villages is eight thousand.

Sample Size: It is better to study the whole District regarding research for the exact results only two villages were selected for study namely Kanju and Dherai. Only 10% respondents were randomly selected which makes total number of ninety. Selection was made according to the following table.

Table 1 Sample respondent's selection

Village Name	Number of Farmers	Respondents
Kanju	500	50
Dherai	400	40
Total	900	90

Source: Farm Services Center (Tehsil Kabal)

The data was taken from Agriculture farm services center and total 10% which makes total of ninety respondents, fifty from village Kanju and forty from village Dherai were selected.

Data Collection: The study was based on primary data; however secondary data was obtained from different resources. For the collection of primary data an interview schedule was designed in the light of objective of the research study. The data was collected through face to face interview.

Analysis of the Data: After the collection of data it was transferred to the computer and analyzed. The analysis was made by applying descriptive statistics (Paired t-test) mainly Mean, Percentages and relevant tests for the interpretation.

Formula for paired t-test:

$$t = \frac{\bar{d}}{sd\sqrt{n}}$$

Where:

\bar{d} = difference between two sample observations

n = number of pairs

sd = standard deviation

$$sd = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(d_i - \bar{d})^2}{n-1}} \text{ and } \bar{d} = \frac{\sum d_i}{n}, \text{ the mean of d-values.}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The main purpose of the current study was to examine the role of formal education in enhancing farm productivity. The survey was conducted in Two villages of district Swat namely Kanju and Dherai.

Age of the Respondents

Age is an important factor in determining a person's interest to participate in development process in any community. Age of an individual makes him mentally mature and able to take rational decisions (Khan,1991). According to the respondents the young people were usually involved in getting education while the old people stop doing farming due to their health. The participation of age group of 31-40 was noted greater than other because they were strong and healthy.

Table 2 Age of sample respondents:

Village	20-30		31-40		41-50		51 and above		Total
	NO.	%	NO.	%	NO.	%	NO.	%	
Kanju	13	26	21	42	10	20	6	12	50
Dherai	7	18	14	35	13	33	6	15	40
Total	20	22	35	39	23	26	12	13	90

Source: Field Survey

Education of the Respondents

According to the United Nations definition literate is a person who can read and write. As to find out the Formal educational level of the respondents, four levels were selected. Most of the farmers have low income and it is very hard for them to continue education so they quit education at early stages and is clear from the table that majority of the respondents have educational up to primary, followed by respondents who have got certificate of matriculation.

Table 3 Educational level of literate respondents

Village	Primary		Middle		Matric		Intermediate		Total
	NO.	%	NO.	%	NO.	%	NO.	%	
Kanju	13	52	6	24	4	16	2	8	25
Dherai	8	40	4	20	5	25	3	15	20
Total	21	47	10	22	9	20	5	11	45

Source: Field Survey

Training attends by Sample Respondents

Table 4 below indicates response of sample respondents about attending trainings organized by extension department on different topics. The literate farmers were more interested in organizing trainings. It is evident that 81% of the respondents attended the trainings arranged by extension department while 17% respondents did not attend trainings arranged by extension department. Either they are not contacted by Extension or farm services department or they were not interested themselves.

Table 4 Training attends by Sample Respondents:

Village	Yes		NO		Total
	NO.	%	NO.	%	
Kanju	37	74	13	26	50
Dherai	36	90	4	10	40
Total	73	81	17	19	90

Source: Field Survey

Response of sample respondents about learning new farming methods

Table 5 indicates learning of new farming methods. It was noted that 33% of sample respondents learned about sowing while 23% learned about irrigation. 24% and 19%, learned about use of fertilizer and harvesting respectively. The ratios were observed different in both villages. According to the sample respondents these new methods increase their skills of farming and helped them in better production. According to the table in village Kanju majority of the respondents 30% have learned new techniques of harvesting and sowing which have positive impact on the production. The second majority is 24% of fertilization and second last 16% of new techniques of irrigation. Similarly in village Dherai the majority 36% learned new techniques of sowing, second majority 31% learned new techniques of irrigation. The third majority of respondents 25% who attend trainings have learned new techniques of fertilization. 8% of respondents learned new techniques of harvesting.

Table 5 Response of sample respondents about learning new farming methods

Village	Sowing		Irrigation		Fertilization		harvesting		Total
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	
Kanju	11	30	6	16	9	24	11	30	37
Dherai	13	36	11	31	9	25	3	8	36
Total	24	33	17	23	18	24.7	14	19	73

Source: Field Survey

Opinion of sample respondents about the increased productivity

Table 6 below indicates response of sample respondents about the increase in the productivity after trainings and knowing new techniques. It is evident that 60% of respondents noted increase in their production while 40% didn't observe any increase. It was noted that 58% and 63% in Kanju and Dherai respectively were of the views that they observed increase in their productivity while 42% and 38% didn't observe any increase in their productivity.

Table 6 Opinion of sample respondents about the increased productivity.

Village	Yes		No		Total
	No.	%	No.	%	
Kanju	29	58	21	42	50
Dherai	25	63	15	38	40
Total	54	60	36	40	90

Source: Field Survey

Value of 50% increase in productivity of sample respondents

Table 7 below indicates about the 50% increase in productivity of respondents before and after applying new techniques. It shows that the total productivity of sample respondents was 80monds before training and it

increased to 115 monds after applying new methods and techniques. Result of t-test is significant which shows that there is a difference in productivity before and after training and applying new techniques.

Table 7 Value of 50% increase in productivity of sample respondents:

Village	Production value(Unit=monds per 1acre)		t-value	p-value
	Before	After		
Kanju	45	60		
Dherai	35	55	-7.523	.001
Total	80	115		

Source: Field Survey

Significant at 5 %

Utilization of increased income of respondents

Table 8 below describes utilization of increased income of sample respondents. In sample respondents of Kanju 31%, 38%, 24% and 7% utilize their increased income in Education, health, agricultural activities and for routine activities, while in village Dherai the sample respondents utilize their increase income in Children education 20%, in Health 44%, in Agricultural Activities 24% and routine expenditure 12%.

Table 8 Utilization of increased income of respondents.

Village	Children education		Health		Agri. Activities		Routine expenditure		Total
	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	
Kanju	9	31	11	38	7	24	2	7	29
Dherai	5	20	11	44	6	24	3	12	25
Total	14	26	22	41	13	24	5	9	54

Source: Field survey

CONCLUSION

Education play important role in every sphere of life. The educated farmers were more aware of their problems and used new techniques to solve it. The conclusion drawn show that maximum number of farmers received trainings on different topics related to farming. Majority has applied new techniques on their farms / land which resulted in better production and increased income. These trainings have also made their work easy. Most of the members received quality agricultural inputs. They found these better as compared to the market inputs. The plots demonstration on farm land has enabled the farmers to learn a lot of farming techniques. The unavailability of farm machinery was a big problem. Some weaknesses were found but as a whole the effect was positive on the farming community. The farmers received a lot of benefits from farm services centers in the study area.

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